

D-1.5. Recommendations and target zones for improved “One Health” surveillance.

Antibiotic Resistance Dynamics (ARDIG): The influence of geographic origin and management systems on resistance gene flows within humans, animals and the environment.

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Background

The increasing resistance to antimicrobials has become one of the most important health threats in Europe and in the world (1). To address this threat, the European Commission launched several European Joint Programmes (EJP) projects such as “Risk and Disease burden of Antimicrobial Resistance” (RADAR) or “Antibiotic Resistance Dynamics: the influence of geographic origin and management systems on resistance gene flows within humans, animals and the environment.” (ARDIG). The results of these projects are of great importance to address the growing AMR challenges.

Conclusions and recommendations from ARDIG

a. On AMU

Antimicrobial use (AMU) is a main influencing factor on antimicrobial resistance (AMR). A list of recommendations on AMU has been generated based on the Antibiotic Resistance Dynamics (ARDIG) project results to tackle AMR (2).

On the medical side:

The data collection of the health care systems differ between countries and sometimes also within countries. As an example, in Northern Ireland, general practitioners prescribe at the request of the secondary care services. In contrast, in England, outpatient medications are provided by hospitals. In such a situation the comparison on either hospital or outpatient prescription data between the two regions is very challenging. It is important to understand and report these differences and efforts should be undertaken, to allow for a harmonization of data. Currently, analyses comparing AMU in humans across systems and countries should be done with care.

In the EU, the agreed unit for antimicrobial use in humans is defined daily doses /1000 inhabitants/day. However, in national reports this unit is not always applied. For instance, a report on primary care in Wales provides AMU data applying other units (STAR-PU Specific Therapeutic Group Age-sex weightings Related Prescribing Units(2)). We suggest that all reports on AMU in humans at the national and regional level should provide data based on the agreed unit as a minimum which does not exclude, additional units used on the national level, e.g. for longer term comparisons.

On the veterinary side:

There is no agreed unit for data on the use of antimicrobials in animals. Monitoring and surveillance systems on AMU apply diverse units based on their specific purposes (3). There is some overlap of systems reporting on the same animal categories. Better use of the available resources could be achieved. Most of these systems are not reporting to the EU level due to this lack of harmonization. A higher level of harmonization would increase the data sharing. ARDIG suggests two different approaches to overcome it:

- a. Define a standard measure fully harmonised for AMU in the animal sector.
- b. Provide numerator and denominator data in national reports that allow transforming one unit into another. The following data would be required to transform all/most of the unit currently used:
 1. the name of the active ingredient,
 2. amount of active ingredient,
 3. number of treated animals,
 4. the population at risk,
 5. the weight of the treated animals,

6. treatment duration and the
7. duration of the therapeutic effect of the active ingredient in the body.

If an agreed unit was suggested, the data requirements would be reduced drastically.

In this regard, the implementation of the Reg (EU) No. 6/2019 on veterinary medicinal products will greatly improve the comparability of data and populations.

Availability of harmonised usage data for animals on production category level would allow enhancing comparative analyses across sectors and countries, such as the JIACRA analyses by EFSA, EMA and ECDC addressing resistance and antimicrobial treatment data.

Important differences in AMU and AMR have been described between different animal species and categories such as broilers and turkeys (4), broilers and laying hens, calves, dairy cows and beef cattle and older fattening pigs and sows, young fattening pigs (<30 kg) and older fattening pigs (5). This suggests that AMU collection by type of production (e.g. broiler or laying hens instead of chicken), animal species (e.g. broilers and turkeys instead of poultry) and age categories when the animal production cycle is long (e.g. calves instead of cattle) would provide a more suitable and accurate data to assess the association between AMU and AMR.

Reports on AMU should always report on the same antimicrobial drug categories for the same animal category that should likewise be defined in a harmonized way.

b. On AMR

A review on data collection systems on AMR in the six ARDIG countries showed that surveillance and monitoring systems vary substantially between countries and between sectors and sometimes even within sectors in a country (2). They often adopt specific standards and their corresponding evaluation criteria. However, frequently these standards do not cover all drug and bacteria combinations. In consequence, different standards and/or evaluation criteria may be used for different drug and bug combinations in the same system. Sometimes data collections on SIR data do not even record the used standards making comparisons across such collections largely inaccurate if not completely futile. Moreover, the monitoring and surveillance systems are neither harmonized across the animal sectors, within and between countries nor are they harmonized with resistance testing in humans.

Data collecting systems on AMR should preferably collect data based on the same standards, and evaluation criteria, and a similar antimicrobial panel. Differences in AMR between clinical and non-clinical isolates in animals (6-8) indicate that preferably both should be collected and that comparisons between the categories need to consider the origin of isolates. Animal categories should be harmonized between clinical and non-clinical isolates as well as between countries in order to compare, evaluate and analyse AMR. Otherwise, data comparisons could

not be in most cases directly addressed. Currently, collection of AMR data on the veterinary side is only harmonized for zoonotic and indicator bacteria, but not for clinical isolates, although efforts have been undertaken to improve this situation (9).

Differences in the applied standards can sometimes be overcome by statistical procedures such as the NRI (normalized resistance interpretation) method or similar approaches to overcome the lack of harmonization on laboratory methods and methodologies (8). However, this requires availability of quantitative values (such as minimum inhibitory concentrations and inhibition zone diameters) across a substantial range of values and therefore cannot be applied i.e. to data obtained by automated systems such as the VITEK. Reports on AMR should however preferably provide quantitative values rather than data on the SIR level.

Differences in the substances tested and the bacterial and host populations included in the testing are also difficult to overcome. For some antimicrobial classes representative substances may be selected as e.g. done in the harmonized monitoring of zoonotic pathogens in the food chain (10). However, for some groups of substances such as the aminoglycosides resistance levels may differ substantially limiting the use of representative substances.

There is lack of harmonization on antimicrobial panels between human and animals and between clinical and non-clinical isolates from livestock. The harmonisation of clinical isolates in livestock would improve this issue. The choice of a harmonised panel in veterinary pathogens should be made by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) based on the scientific studies (11, 12). A further step might be the antimicrobial panel harmonization between clinical and non-clinical isolates in livestock. It could be achieved if those drugs defined only in one of the harmonized antimicrobial panels would be at least a part of the data reported by the other panel. This would ensure uniformity.

As observed for the AMU-systems, overlap between systems within countries is also observed, albeit less frequently as in the field of antimicrobial consumption and use.

c. On AMU and AMR

Due to the lack of system harmonization on AMU and AMR addressed previously, only a small portion of data are reported at the EU level.

A large number of AMU and AMR collecting systems were found per country and sector. Some overlap between monitoring and surveillance systems on AMU and AMR was encountered. Therefore, the performance of some resources could be improved by reducing the number of overlapping systems. However, some overlap between collecting systems may be convenient for system and data validation. Overlap between reports has been encountered as a logical consequence of the overlap presence between systems.

AMU and AMR reports are published in different languages and time ranges. Therefore, they should be provided annually in one international language (e.g. English) to ease published data access.

References

1. European Commission. Proposal for a COUNCIL REGULATION establishing the Joint Undertakings under Horizon Europe. 2021.
2. Mesa-Varona O, Chaintarli K, Muller-Pebody B, Anjum M, Eckmanns T, Norström M, et al. Monitoring Antimicrobial Resistance and Drug Usage in the Human and Livestock Sector and Foodborne Antimicrobial Resistance in Six European Countries. *Infection and Drug Resistance*. 2020;Volume 13:957-93.
3. Sanders P, Vanderhaeghen W, Fertner M, Fuchs K, Obritzhauser W, Agunos A, et al. Monitoring of Farm-Level Antimicrobial Use to Guide Stewardship: Overview of Existing Systems and Analysis of Key Components and Processes. *Front Vet Sci*. 2020;7:540.
4. Mesa-Varona O, Kaspar H, Grobbel M, Tenhagen B-A. Phenotypical antimicrobial resistance data of clinical and non-clinical *Escherichia coli* from poultry in Germany between 2014 and 2017. *Plos One*. 2020;15(12):e0243772.
5. Merle R, Hajek P, Kasbohrer A, Hegger-Gravenhorst C, Mollenhauer Y, Robanus M, et al. Monitoring of antibiotic consumption in livestock: a German feasibility study. *Prev Vet Med*. 2012;104(1-2):34-43.
6. Tenhagen B-A, Käsbohrer A, Grobbel M, Hammerl JA, Kaspar H. Antibiotikaresistenz von *E. coli* aus Rinderpopulationen in Deutschland. *Tierärztliche Praxis - Ausgabe Großtiere*. 2020;48(4):218-27.
7. Mesa-Varona O, Kaspar H, Grobbel M, Tenhagen BA. Phenotypical antimicrobial resistance data of clinical and non-clinical *Escherichia coli* from poultry in Germany between 2014 and 2017. *PLoS One*. 2020;15(12):e0243772.
8. Mesa-Varona O, Mader R, Velasova M, Madec JY, Granier SA, Perrin-Guyomard A, et al. Comparison of Phenotypical Antimicrobial Resistance between Clinical and Non-Clinical *E. coli* Isolates from Broilers, Turkeys and Calves in Four European Countries. *Microorganisms*. 2021;9(4).
9. Mader R, Damborg P, Amat JP, Bengtsson B, Bourelly C, Broens EM, et al. Building the European Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance network in veterinary medicine (EARS-Vet). *Euro Surveill*. 2021;26(4).
10. Aerts M, Battisti A, Hendriksen R, Kempf I, Teale C, Tenhagen BA, et al. Technical specifications on harmonised monitoring of antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic and indicator bacteria from food-producing animals and food. *Efsa Journal*. 2019;17(6):122.
11. Teale C, Borriello P. A proposed scheme for the monitoring of antibiotic resistance in veterinary pathogens of food animals in the UK. *Veterinary Record*. 2021;n/a(n/a):e201.
12. Mader R, Bourély C, Amat J-P, Broens EM, Busani L, Callens B, et al. Defining the scope of the European Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance network in Veterinary medicine (EARS-Vet): a bottom-up and One Health approach. *bioRxiv*. 2021:2021.03.09.434124.